

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Study title: Foodways: Exploring household and community food practices

INVITATION

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY?

The purpose of this study is to understand more about peoples' food practices in the home and neighbourhood.

WHY HAVE I BEEN INVITED TO PARTICIPATE?

You have been invited to participate because you are an adult resident of either London Borough of Tower Hamlets or city of Brighton and Hove. We are interested in people's understandings of food and we think you will have ideas and experiences which we think are important for researchers and policy makers to understand.

DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

No! It is up to you to decide whether to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and will be asked to sign a consent form. You are however still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO ME IF I TAKE PART?

You will take part in one or more of the following activities with one or more of the researchers:

- *Fridge/cupboards talks* - discussing food items and storage practices in your fridge/cupboards
- *Food maps* – *mapping* your food shopping journeys and the items in chosen meals
- *Cook-alongs*– preparing a meal that you regularly have
- *Shop-along* - going on your usual food shop

During these activities, researcher(s) will accompany you, while taking notes, videos and audio-recordings and photographs with your consent. Participants will receive a small recompense in the form of a shopping voucher for their time and any expenses.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE DISADVANTAGES AND RISKS OF TAKING PART?

The primary disadvantage of participating in this study is the time taken to participate. Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress that can be generated by discussing food will be kept to the minimum through the activities chosen, and the experience of the researchers. Dr Elaine Swan has received training in counselling skills and the researchers are experienced in qualitative research about food. By employing exploratory research methods and an open structure to the discussions, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

By taking part in this study you are helping to expand knowledge on food practices in your neighbourhood and council area which can potentially influence future food-related policies. This data will be of potential benefit in informing the agendas of organisations concerned with food distribution within the area.

WILL MY INFORMATION IN THIS STUDY BE KEPT CONFIDENTIAL?

All information collected about you will be kept strictly confidential. Confidentiality, privacy and anonymity will be ensured through strict adherence to the guidelines for storing, managing and processing data set out in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018.

After the undertaking the research methods, only the researchers will have access to your data. We will keep all personal information about you (e.g. your name and other information about you that can identify you) confidential, that is we will not share it with others. We will also anonymise the written transcript produced by the transcriber. This means that we will remove any personal information.

This research project may involve the use of University of Sussex Zoom. Details of the platform's privacy notice can be found here: [Zoom Privacy Policy](#). All audio-visual data collected will be downloaded and stored securely on a University of Sussex managed storing system, named OneDrive.

WHAT SHOULD I DO IF I WANT TO TAKE PART?

To opt in for the study, please agree to take part by signing the consent form.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY?

The results of this research study will be used to inform several academic pieces of work. These may include: articles in published academic journals, academic book chapters, public presentations, conferences and/or events. Copies of any research output will be made freely available to all participants, although participants should note that this process is planned to take place over a 4-year period, with data retained for the length of that period. When writing up the findings from this study, we would like to reproduce some of the views and ideas you shared with us. We will only use anonymised quotes so that although we will use your exact words, we will do our best to ensure you cannot be identified in the publications, although we cannot guarantee this.

WHO IS ORGANISING AND FUNDING THE RESEARCH?

Research will be undertaken by members of the Management Department and Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU) at the University of Sussex. The project is part of a larger UKRI research study entitled 'Transforming Food Systems for Disadvantaged Communities', which is administered at the University of Reading.

WHO HAS APPROVED THIS STUDY?

The study has been approved by the Social Sciences & Arts Cross-Schools Research Ethics Committee (SSARTA) at the University of Sussex. The ethical review application numbers is [XX/XXXX/X].

CONTACT FOR FURTHER INFORMATION

If you require any additional information, please contact Dr Elaine Swan by emailing e.swan@sussex.ac.uk. Any concerns regarding the way in which the study has been conducted should be directed toward [X] (Chair of the C-REC who reviewed the project) by emailing [X].

INSURANCE

The University of Sussex has insurance in place to cover its legal liabilities in respect of this study.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet. Any participation is greatly appreciated.